

KICHIK YOSHDAGI BOLALAR NUTQINI O'STIRISHDA MAQOLLARNING AHAMIYATI

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***Annotatsiya:** Mazkur maqolada bolalarni kichik yoshidan boshlab maqollar yordamida dunyoqarashini o'stirishning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Maqollarni bolalar kamolotidagi o'rni tahlil qilib berilgan.*

***Kalit so'z va iboralar:** kichik yosh, maqol, xalq og'zaki ijodi.*

***Аннотация:** В данной статье освещено значение развития мировоззрения детей с раннего возраста с помощью пословиц. Анализируется роль пословиц в развитии детей.*

***Ключевые слова и фразы:** младший возраст, пословица, устное народное творчество.*

***Annotation:** In this article , the importance of raising the worldview of children from a young age with help of Proverbs is reflected. The proverbs are given as an analysis of the role of children in maturation.*

***Keys words and word expressions:** little age , proverb , oral creativity of the people.*

Ma'lumki har qaysi xalq , yoki millatning tafakkuri, turmush tarzi, ma'naviy qarashlari o'z-o'zidan bo'sh joyda shakllanib qolmaydi. Ularning vujudga kelishi va rivojlanishida aniq tarixiy , tabiiy va ijtimoiy omillar asos bo'lishini hammamiz yaxshi bilamiz. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarning asosiy vazifalardan biri bu nutqini o'stirishdir. Ya'ni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida badiiy adabiyotning janrlari orqali o'stiriladi. Oilada , bolalar uchun maqollar , ertaklar , hikoyalar aytib yoki o'qib berish orqali bolalar nutqini o'stirishga erishiladi . Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilot tarbiyachilari esa shu badiiy adabiyotni janrlari orqali bolalar nutqi o'sishini

mustahkamlaydi. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida kunning har qismida badiiy adabiyotning janrlariga yuzlanamiz. Bizga ma'lumki, xalq yaratgan g'oyat ixcham, chuqur va tugal ma'noli gaplar maqol deb yuritiladi. Maqollar xalqning, bir necha avlodlarning aql-u farosati hamda turmush tajribasining yakuni, ular donishmandlarning mahsulidir. Maqollarda hayotning achchiq-chuchugini tatib ko'rgan, turmushidagi hodisalarga aql ko'zi bilan qaraydigan, sof vijdonli, oliyjanob, mehnatkash kishining biror voqea-hodisadan, biror kishidan yoki biror ishdan chiqargan xulosasi bayon qilinadi. Bu xulosa biror kishi uchun (ko'proq bolalar uchun) yo'l ko'rsatuvchi bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin. Maqollar xalqning aql-idroki, ijtimoiy-tarixiy tajribasi, kurashi hamda mehnatining badiiy ifodasi sifatida yaratilib kelinmoqda. Maqollar chuqur ma'noni ifoda eta bilishi, ixcham, pishiq va puxtaligi bilan xalq og'zaki ijodining boshqa turlaridan farq qiladi. Ularda mehnatkash xalqning orzu-umidlari, o'zaro munosabatlari, vatanparvarlik, insonparvarlik hislatlari, o'y-fikrlari o'ziga xos shaklda aks etgan bo'ladi. Shu sababdan ular bolalarni to'g'ri, mantiqiy fikrlashga, maqsadni qisqa, ixcham va lo'nda bayon etishga o'rgatadi, ularning badiiy didini oshiradi, tarixiy hodisalarning mohiyatini yaxshiroq, chuqurroq payqab olishga yordam beradi. Bundan tashqari, maqollar ona tilining eng nozik badiiy xususiyatlarini bilishga va so'z boyligini oshirishga ko'maklashuvchi vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Kuzatishlarimizdan shunday xulosaga keldikki, deyarli maqollarda, birinchi navbatda bola tarbiyasi, odob yotar ekan. E'tibor bering:

“Avval salom, keyin kalom”, “Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla”, “Bola aziz, odobi undan aziz”, “Inson odobi bilan, osmon oftobi bilan”, “Odob bozorda sotilmas”, “Odobning boshi til”, “Yaxshi xulq kishining husni” bunday iboralarimiz maqollar ro'yhatini yana cho'zish mumkin. Bola kamolotida birinchi navbatda, salom-alik turadi. Salom-alikni o'rgangan, uni kanda qilmaydigan har bir bolaning ishi yurishadi, omadi chopaveradi. Xalqimiz maqollarni yoqtiradi. Shu bois u ming yillar jarayonida million marta qayta-qayta sinovdan o'tkazib, bu haqda ta'siri, foydali, har bir inson amal qilsa,

ibrat olib yashasa , aslo dard qolmasligi mumkinligi to'g'risida yuzlab maqollar to'qigan . Kichik yoshdagi bolalarda vatan haqida maqollarni yod oldirish orqali ularda ona vatanga nisbatan hurmat , faxr , mehr hissini uyg'otishi mumkin . Kichik chog'idan vatan uchun kurashadigan , kerak bo'lsa , jonini fido qiladigan , mard , dovyurak farzand bo'lishiga xizmat qiladi .Demak , insonning tug'ilib o'sgan joyi , ya'ni kindik to'kilgan maskan uni vatani ekanligini his qiladi.Insonning o'zi , uyi – oilasi , ona-Vatani tinch bo'lsa , bu bitmas-tuganmas shodlik , baxt . Mana shu baxt uchun kurashish g'oyasini kichkintoy qalbiga singdirib borish foydadan holi bo'lmaydi . Shu nuqtai nazardan quyidagi maqol muhim tarbiyaviy ahamiyat kasb etadi :

Ona yurtning omon bo'lsa ,

Rangi ro'ying somon bo'lmas .

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki , xalq maqollarida yaxshilik , halollik , to'g'rilik hamda rostgo'ylik ulug'lanib , yomonlik , yolg'onchilik va qalloblik qoralanadi . Yuqoridagi sharxlardan ko'rinadiki , xalq maqolini qo'llab , yetti o'lchab bir kesib yashagan inson hech qachon kam bo'lmaydi . Hozirgi paytda ham maqol janiri takomillashib , bolalarning ong-tushunchalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda . Shunday ekan , bolalarni kichik yoshidan boshlab , xalq maqollari asosida tarbiyalash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi .

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